

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN SPIRITUAL EDUCATION

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[https://doi.org/ 10.5281/zenodo.6657898](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657898)

Annatation: Mazkur maqolada jismoniy tarbiya va sportning shaxsni ma'naviy tarbiyalashdagi ahamiyati o'rganilgan. Bu masalani o'rganish uchun zarur bo'lgan ta'riflar berilgan. Sportning insonning ma'naviy fazilatlarini shakllantirishga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadigan omillar ko'rib chiqilgan.

Keywords: jismoniy tarbiya; jismoniy madaniyat; sport, ruhiy tarbiya.

Physical culture is part of a culture aimed at strengthening and maintaining health. It represents a set of certain values, knowledge and norms applied by society for physical, mental and moral qualities, the comprehensive development of physical education.

The main purpose of physical education is to optimize a person's physical development, as well as to comprehensively improve the physical qualities and abilities associated with each person. All this characterizes a socially active person along with cultivating spiritual and moral qualities.

In addition, the goals of physical education are to ensure that every member of society is prepared for productive work and other activities.

In order to achieve these goals in physical education, a set of specific and general pedagogical tasks reflecting the multifaceted nature of education, including the stages of development of learners, the level of preparation, as well as the conditions of preparation are addressed. achieve goals.

In the learning process, special attention is paid to the physical education of the individual. Man's moral character, as well as his will and purposefulness, depend in many ways on him.

It is advisable to start physical education from childhood, because the child develops from an early age, develops learning to be responsible, has the will and endurance, which allows him to become a fully developed person later.

When talking about the current tasks of physical education in terms of its impact on the spiritual and moral aspects of the individual, we can highlight a number of tasks listed below.

- fostering a healthy lifestyle;

- fostering the nature of mutual assistance in the community and among people;
- injustice, dishonesty, intolerance, upbringing;
- The formation of the need for regular physical education and sports in children;
- cultivate such qualities as self-control, courage, willpower;
- developing the ability to cope with difficulties;
- The formation of skills to take care of their health, physical development, self-control over physical and sports training [3, 320].

However, it is not enough to keep the body in good condition and physical activity to develop a person's moral qualities.

Physical education contributes to the harmonious development of the individual and his spiritual qualities only in conjunction with moral, labor, mental, aesthetic education and upbringing. Let's see how this is done in practice.

Sport allows a person to shape properly. Through physical education and sports, moral education is carried out in the form of games, competitions, in which character traits such as will, courage, discipline and endurance are developed.

Labor education is reflected in the great physical stresses that a person is burdened with. These loads accustom the body to work, making a person resilient and purposeful. Thus, as a result of exercise and constant stress, a person is able to withstand various types of work, both physically and mentally.

Long-term loads undoubtedly increase stress tolerance, which is essential in the process of studying and working [2]. In addition, during training, a person becomes fully focused, which means that he involuntarily increases his attention span, perceives information differently, and ultimately develops visual and mechanical memory. Thus, the mental training of the individual is carried out.

Finally, let's talk about the aesthetic component of physical education. Often people are preoccupied with the desire to please themselves in the mirror. Gradually, he improves the quality of his body and creates the beautiful image he wants in his head. It should also be noted that some sports provide aesthetic pleasure. Among them are dance, gymnastics, figure skating. Dealing with them has a great influence on the formation of a person's taste, the idea of beauty.

As mentioned above, sports and physical education serve as a unique field for the formation of personal qualities, leadership, moral and physical training in various stressful life situations. A person will have the ability to demonstrate his willpower qualities, endurance and resilience in physical culture classes. In addition, sports teach you to calculate your strength and move effectively in a limited amount of time.

Let us now consider what methods are used to bring up a person morally through physical training.

In the process of physical education and sports, two main methods are used to develop the spiritual qualities of an individual: play and competition.

The game method focuses on developing agility, strength, speed, ingenuity, independence and initiative. I would also like to emphasize that conscious discipline and collectivism are evolving. That is, everything a person needs in the early stages of socialization and formation as a person is obtained precisely in the process of play. It can be seen that this method is preferable to working with children and, moreover, unlike its competitor, the play method is easier for the child.

Why is the competitive method difficult for children? His distinguishing feature is the fight for the championship. The competitive factor creates a special emotional background that contributes to the maximum manifestation of the body's capabilities. And a small child may not be able to cope with it [1,352]. However, you should not strictly forbid the use of this method when working with children, but gradually you should prepare them mentally for the competition.

Any competition puts a person in front of the need to maximize their capabilities, and at the same time, they need to control themselves in the most difficult situations. The competitive method develops the ability to behave, purposefulness and perseverance.

A particularly important element of personality development in physical education is the quality of the relationship between coach and student. They should be based primarily on mutual respect and be benevolent.

The coach should have a specific "standard" of discipline and accuracy in the student's eyes. A positive educational impact can be expected only in the context of pedagogically oriented activities, such as when the teacher gives ethical examples or gives exercises that require self-overcoming [4,125-128].

The impact of physical education and sports on a person helps to improve his personal abilities and qualities, which ultimately leads to his all-round development.

Thus, it can be said that the role of physical education in the spiritual formation of an individual is very great. One must be able to think abstractly, behave and be disciplined.

However, it is not enough to think and draw conclusions. You need to be able to put these conclusions into practice in life, to achieve your goal, to overcome difficulties along the way.

You can do this with the right physical training. Thus, with a close connection between physical and mental upbringing and only complete harmony between them, we can expect the full development of a person's moral qualities.

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